

Experiences of Non-criminology Graduates Police Officers in Philippine National Police (PNP) Organization

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ABSTRACT

The experiences of non-criminology graduate police officers in the Philippine National Police organization are necessary to perceive whether internal and external factors affect their motivation and decision to enter the organization. This study will explore the experiences of non-criminology graduate Police officers in the Philippine National Police (PNP) organization during the year 2023. Transcendental phenomenology was the research design used in the study. Six non-criminology graduate police officers in the Philippine National Police organization participated in the study and were chosen using purposive sampling. An in-depth interview was done to gather data using interview guide questions. The participants' responses were transcribed, coded, and organized to form themes based on the study's objective with the aid of Hyperresearch software. The data were then analyzed and interpreted using Moustaka's data analysis steps. Results revealed that the majority of the non-criminology graduate police officers were at the age of middle age, with a degree in Education, and with rank as Police Staff Sergeants. Non-criminology graduate police officers experienced having motivation for joining PNP, positive experience during Basic Recruit Training (BRT), receiving equal treatment during BRT, challenges during BRT, overcoming personal weaknesses, and a variety of coping mechanisms in dealing with challenges during BRT. They have a strong sense of purpose, and commitment to public service can be a powerful motivator for anyone seeking a career in law enforcement, regardless of their academic background. They have also found that their unique skills and perspectives from their previous academic or professional backgrounds are valued and contribute to their success during BRT and beyond. They used to have different skills and experiences than their criminology graduate peers. However, they are held to the same high professionalism, discipline, and ethical conduct standards. They face certain challenges due to their lack of formal training or Education in law enforcement; however, with dedication, hard work, and a willingness to learn, non-criminology graduate police officers can overcome their challenges and become successful law enforcement officers. They used to face personal weaknesses during BRT in the PNP; they can overcome them by setting goals, seeking out mentorship and support, and staying committed to their development as a law enforcement officer. They used to adopt a growth mindset, meaning that they view challenges as opportunities for growth and learning.

Keywords: Challenges; Coping mechanisms; Equal treatment; Motivation; Overcoming weaknesses; Positive experience.

1. Introduction

Most people are becoming captivated by criminology and criminal justice careers because they are influenced by popular shows such as Law and Order, CSI, Criminal Minds, and Sherlock Holmes (Roufa, 2017). Criminology investigates crime as a criminal act that society punishes through the judicial system and focuses on the causes, prevention, and correction of crime areas (Maryville University, 2022).

Criminology also helps to prepare students for the real world. It allows them to learn about the criminal justice system and how to apply their knowledge in a practical setting (Lebeouf, 2023). It also helps them build their network of contacts in the field (Manhiem & Bernard, 2019). In the Philippines, Criminology Education includes Criminal Law and Jurisprudence programs, Law Enforcement Administration, Forensic Science, Crime Detection, Correctional Administration, and Criminal Sociology (Republic Act No. 11131).

Non-criminology graduates are those professionals who are not graduates of the College of Criminology, such as doctors, engineers, computer technicians, teachers, and others (Weaver, 2022). They are those professionals who did not study crime to reduce and prevent it (Your dictionary). Non-criminology graduates are skilled workers but inexpert in gathering, handling evidence, and disassembling and reassembling firearms (Bestschoolchoice, 2022).

Non-criminology graduates do not look at criminal behavior from an individual and society perspective (Dees, 2021). They do not have a wide range of connected subjects, including the incidence of lawlessness, its effects on common people and the country, and responses to offenses (Indeed Editorial Team, 2023)

The experiences of non-criminology graduate police officers in the Philippine National Police organization are necessary to perceive whether internal and external factors affect their motivation and decision to enter the organization (Mojares et al., 2017). It is also significant for non-criminology graduates to pursue their dreams as public servants by joining the police organization even if they are not graduates of the College of Criminology (Cepeda, 2020). The experiences of police officers in the organization are also beneficial to those who are out of choice in picking their job interest which later they come up with an overview of being a police officer who is not graduated from the College of Criminology (Anderson, 2019). It is also relevant today, where most non-criminology are hired by the Philippine National Police, such as IT graduates, nurses, doctors, teachers, and social workers (Caliwan, 2019). The experiences of police officers are also the advantages of the College of Criminology, whether or not there are advantages of being a criminology graduate in pursuing a police career, such as the terms, training, and guidelines in police organization (Patty, 2022).

The Police organization, such as Philippine National Police, is a line and staff organization that separates the frontline and support units (Taguig City University, 2021). Non-criminology graduate Police officers are essential in the administrative support units of PNP like Chaplain Services, Engineering Services, and Finance Services which most of them consists of chaplains, doctors, accountant, and others whose profession is suitable to their environment (Gobyerknows, 2021). Additionally, non-criminology police officers are also in operational support units such as Medical and Dental Centers and the Civil Relations Unit, composed of skilled and professional workers, particularly dentists, teachers, and social workers (Dalizon, 2023). The non-criminology mentioned above graduate police officers is such an example to conduct a study on their experiences in the Philippine National Police organization. The researchers are concerned and sought to recognize the experiences of non-criminology graduate police officers in the Philippine National Police organization.

2. Methods

This study used the qualitative research approach. The transcendental phenomenological design was used to obtain the data or the interviewee's response in a sequence of formulating a theme of their overall responses. Transcendental phenomenology is a form of qualitative research that focuses on studying an individual's lived experiences within the world (Neubauer, Witkop, & Varpio, 2019). This research design is suited to explore the situation, challenges, and experiences encountered by the non-criminology Police officer currently serving in the Philippine National Police (PNP) organization.

The study was conducted in the Philippine National Police under the command of Police Regional Office 10, specifically in the PNP stations of the Province of Lanao del Norte and Misamis Occidental. The AOR of PRO 10 covers five (5) provinces, namely: Bukidnon, Camiguin, Lanao del Norte, Misamis Occidental, and Misamis Oriental; two (2) highly urbanized cities of Cagayan de Oro and Iligan; seven (7) component cities of Oroquieta, Ozamis, Tangub all in Misamis Occ, Gingoog and El Salvador in Misamis Or, and Malaybalay and Valencia in

Bukidnon; 84 municipalities; and 2,022 barangays. It has a population of 3,505,558 with a total land area of 19,279 sq. kilometers. The people are a happy mixture of three (3) ethnic-culture, namely: the Christians, which are the predominant group, followed by the Muslims, and the cultural community groups. Almost 80% of the populace originates from the Visayas region, 10% from Luzon, and 10% from different parts of the country. The Cebuano dialect is dominant in most places of the region. The general topography of the region is characterized by rugged mountains ranges (Mount Balatucan Mountain Range in Misamis Oriental, Mount Kitanglad and Kalatungan Mountain Ranges in Bukidnon, and Mt Malindang and Mt Ampiro Ranges in Misamis Occidental), coastal plains, plateaus, rivers which flows southward from Bukidnon towards the Rio Grande in Cotabato.

This study was participated by six (6) non-criminology graduate Police officers currently serving in the PNP organization. These participants were purposely identified and chosen based on the following criteria: 1. Serving at least two (2) years in a PNP organization, and 2.) Non-criminology graduates.

The study used the interview guide crafted by certified researchers. The certified psychologist validated the instrument since the study was also connected to experiences. The researcher also used an audio recorder during the interview of the participants. The researcher set an appointment with the identified participants and proposed the interview schedule. The researcher informed the participants that the conversation would be recorded and assured them that all their responses would be confidential. Further, the minimum health protocol was observed during the interview, considering the pandemic.

In the current study, the researcher always observed the ethical standards. The researcher strictly upheld all study participants' voluntary participation. Participants were allowed to sign the informed consent form that the researcher had created, which ensured that the interview was conducted with their express consent. In terms of the participant's identity, the researcher applied the measure to promote anonymity and secrecy by not mentioning my participants' names during the interview. Privacy and confidentiality were always observed, particularly the names of the participants and other information unnecessary to the study. The researcher adheres to the Republic Act No. 10173 guidelines, known as the "Data Privacy Act of 2012".

This study will use Moustakas' (1994) data analysis technique of phenomenological reduction. The transcripts of all participants gathered from the interviews will be analyzed using the methods of Moustakas. The following are the steps in the phenomenological reduction which serves as a guide in analyzing the data gathered: (1) Bracketing, (2) Horizontalization, (3) Clustering into Themes, (4) Textural Description, (5) Structural Description, and (6) Textural-Structural Synthesis.

Bracketing is an approach which the researchers will use to mitigate the effects of preconceived notions and perceptions held before the study commences. It is a process of suspending judgments and biases, or 'epoche.' Consequently, the researchers will reach a deep level of inquiry from topic and population selection, interview design, collection and interpretation, and dissemination of research findings.

Horizontalization technically refers to listing all the verbatim expressions that will have a bearing on the study. Initially, the researchers will look into each statement with equal value. Then, statements that will be found irrelevant, repetitive, overlapping, and outside the scope of the study will be ignored. Finally, horizons, the

remaining sections after the data has been polished, will be considered as the constituent and meaningful parts of the phenomenon. Moustakas states, "Horizons are unlimited, and horizontalization is a never-ending process" (Moustakas, 1994).

Clustering is the third step in obtaining inferences from the study. It involves the reduction of experiences to invariant horizons, creating core themes, and validating the invariant horizons using multiple data sources. In reducing the statements into horizons, the researchers will cluster them into themes and ensure that each theme is implied with only one meaning. This is considered as placing the phenomenon into a "textural language." To validate the invariant horizons obtained from the study, the researchers will review the findings of research studies using methods other than the data-gathering methods used in the study, like observation, field note-taking, focus group interviews, and related literature. This validation process is crucial to the accuracy and clarity of the representations.

Textural description, or 'what occurred,' refers to an account that describes the perception of the phenomenon. In obtaining the textural description of the participants' experience, the researchers will use the verbatim excerpts from the interview and provide a narration of the meaning units derived from the themes. Structural description, or how it occurred, integrates imaginative variation, an ingenious outlook, and insights into the textural description. An imaginative variation is considered the mental experiment on analyzing the details and structures of the participants' experience by being detached from natural inclination through epoche. It is appended in each paragraph of textural descriptions to generate a structural description.

In the textural-structural synthesis process, the researchers will collate the meaning units of each participant and develop a composite of textural and structural descriptions that are common to them. A narrative or synthesis represents all participants written in a third-person perspective. The primary goal of this final step of Moustakas' method is to obtain the essence of the experience of the phenomenon. Responses of the participants of the study were analyzed through the Hyperresearch software that produces the final themes of the study.

3. Results and Discussions

This qualitative research explored the experiences of non-criminology graduate police officers in the Philippine National Police (PNP) organization. The study participants were six (6) non-criminology graduate police officers in selected stations of Ozamiz City. They were already working in the field.

3.1. Profile of the Non-criminology Graduate Police Officers

Most non-criminology graduate police officer participants are in the 31-40 age range, which may indicate that this age range is a common point of non-criminology graduate police officers where they have acquired enough experience in the Philippine National Police organization. However, it is important to remember that age alone does not necessarily determine the officer's experience, as individual factors such as training, Education, and personal qualities also play an important role. Furthermore, there was also diversity in age among the non-criminology graduate police officer participants, with some falling in the younger age range of 21-30 and others in the older range of 41-50. This implies that there are non-criminology graduate police officers from various career phases and life experiences in the force, which can offer a variety of viewpoints and skills in various

circumstances. Therefore, it is crucial to value and respect the experiences and contributions of police officers of all ages.

Many non-criminology graduate police officers have a degree in Education, and some have Accountancy and Information Technology (IT). It implies that the Philippine National Police (PNP) has different diversity of non-criminology graduate police officers, which could help the organization utilize its community experiences and expertise.

For example, a police officer with a degree in Education, either from seminary or Secondary Education, is more capable in public speaking and community relation. They may also have different social networks and support systems than their accountancy and IT colleagues. On the other hand, a police officer with a degree in accountancy and IT has priorities and interests compared to their education degree colleagues, and they may face different challenges related to work-life balance and personal relationships.

The non-criminology graduate police officers participants are represented in different ranks within the force, with the police staff sergeant participants being half in number to the patrolman/patrolwoman. This shows that police personnel without criminology degrees can ascend to higher ranks within the organization, providing them with increased opportunities for leadership and influence in shaping the policies and practices of the police force. It is important to have diversity and representation within law enforcement to ensure that all voices and perspectives are heard and valued.

According to Dr. Lersch, diversity in law enforcement is critical for effective policing, and non-criminology graduates can bring valuable skills and perspectives to the field (Lersch, 2021). By broadening their recruitment pool beyond criminology graduates, law enforcement agencies can tap into a wider range of knowledge and expertise from social work, psychology, and business. This can lead to improved problem-solving abilities, communication skills, and cultural competencies among law enforcement officers.

In terms of the age distribution of non-criminology graduate police officers, according to a report by the Bureau of Justice Statistics (BJS) from 2017, the median age of full-time state and local law enforcement officers was 39 years old. This suggests that the 31-40 age range may be a common point of non-criminology graduate police officers who are still in service. They gained enough experience and skills to become effective police officers.

One theory to explain why non-criminology graduates are joining law enforcement is the “attraction-selection-attrition” theory. This theory suggests that individuals are attracted to certain professions based on their characteristics, and those with the necessary traits are more likely to be selected for and remain in the profession. Police departments must be aware of and address these barriers to ensure that women have equal opportunities to advance in their careers (Holland, 1959). This may create opportunities for individuals from diverse educational backgrounds to join law enforcement, as agencies may be more willing to consider applicants who have not necessarily pursued a degree in criminology.

Non-criminology graduates in law enforcement may bring different perspectives, skills, and experiences to the profession. This could lead to a more diverse and inclusive law enforcement workforce that is better equipped to understand and serve diverse communities.

Table 1. Profile of the Participants (n=6)

Profile	Frequency	Percentage
Age		
21-23	1	17.00
31-40	3	50.00
41-50	2	33.00
Degree		
Education	3	50.00
Accountancy	2	33.00
Information Technology	1	17.00
Rank		
Patrolman/Patrolwoman	2	33.00
Police Staff Sergeant	4	67.00

Experiences of Non-criminology Graduate Police Officers in the Philippine National Police Organization Participants expressed their experiences in the Philippine National Police (PNP) Organization. The common insights they have based on their responses resulted in six themes that emerged from the data analysis: 1) having motivation for joining PNP; 2) having a positive experience during the Basic Recruit Training (BRT); 3) receiving equal treatment during the BRT; 4) challenges during the BRT; 5) overcoming personal weaknesses; and 6) variety of coping mechanism in dealing with challenges during BRT.

Having Motivation for Joining the Philippine National Police (PNP) One of the experiences of the non-criminology graduate police officers in the PNP organization is having the motivation to join PNP. Participants mentioned various reasons for joining the PNP, such as financial stability to support their family, securing a government job, and proving themselves to others. These were supported by the lines of the participants.

“Financial stability to enable me to provide for my family and my child.” (P5)

“My motivation to become a police officer is to earn a living and have a stable job to support my family.” (P6)

“For my family, I must go above and beyond to support them in the future.” (P4)

“For my family and me, I must finish what I started.” (P3)

“It has good salary and lifetime, secured life because you are a government and it is regular job. Family, and my willingness to join the PNP and to prove myself and to other people that I can make it.” (P1)

Some studies support the motivations for joining Philippine National Police. The motivation of police officers was due to a desire to serve the community, job security, and personal interest in police work (Icaronom et al., 2021).

Their motivation was also to serve the country and protect the community, which includes wanting to be part of a respected institution and having a sense of duty to uphold the law (Mamaril & King, 2018). The most common motivation for joining the PNP was a stable job and a good salary (Navarro, 2019).

Individuals motivated to join the PNP are more likely to be committed to their job and perform better. They may have a greater sense of purpose and job satisfaction, leading to higher engagement and retention. Motivated police officers may also be more willing to undergo training and professional development, which can improve their skills and enhance their performance on the job.

Positive Experience during the Basic Recruit Training

The non-criminology graduate police officers mentioned that their non-criminology background, such as skills in reading comprehension, writing, and speaking, was advantageous in certain aspects of police work and could be applied in other areas of life as well. Participants uttered these lines.

“Because I am a graduate of seminary, I am more adept at reading comprehension and writing, as well as speaking in front of everyone.” (P1)

“I am good at reporting and making reports.” (P2)

“Being knowledgeable about technology gives me an advantage in police office activity.” (P4)

A positive training experience can lead to greater job satisfaction and a more positive attitude toward the profession (Anderson & Cresswell, 2018). Positive relationships and effective communication between the two groups can lead to a more positive training experience (King, 2020). Emotional intelligence was positively associated with officers' ability to adapt to new situations and handle stress (Savicki & Cooley, 2020).

Positive experiences can improve the quality of law enforcement services provided to the community. When recruits receive adequate training, support, and positive reinforcement, they are more likely to develop the necessary skills, knowledge, and attitudes to carry out their duties effectively and professionally. This can help to promote public trust and confidence in law enforcement and reduce instances of misconduct and excessive use of force.

Challenges in Basic Recruit Training

Non-criminology graduate police officers express their experiences and challenges during basic recruit training. They faced challenges during physical training, including difficulties with agility, BMI, and physical endurance, and struggles with the demands of physical training due to a lack of prior fitness experience and a low tolerance for certain conditions such as cold weather. These claims were supported by the lines of participants.

“It was hard for me to adjust for the first three weeks of training.” (P6)

“The difficulties of the physical and agility training as well as the demands on the wallet and field boredom I don't have any friends or other people I can seek aid from because we are all strangers on the training grounds.” (P4)

“I am not used to do fitness like push ups but it is not a hindrance for my success instead I make it as my motivation and later on I made it to Top in agility.” (P1).

“I easily get exhausted in every training because I struggle with fatigue from training because I’ve never been a big exerciser before.” (P3).

“The weather is very cold because we are at Mt. Banahao and I have a low tolerance for coldness.” (P2).

Non-criminology graduate police officers have a knowledge gap, including unfamiliarity with different types of laws, fingerprint analysis, and other criminology-specific terms. These were uttered by participants 1 and 2.

“When it comes to knowledge, it is more advantageous to those who have graduated in criminology compared to others, because I didn’t know such things as arresto mayor and arresto minor.” (P1)

“I don’t know different terms like fingerprint and don’t know how to read it.” (P2)

Recruits with higher levels of physical fitness were more likely to succeed in training, but many struggled to meet fitness standards and required additional support and training (Ramsay et al., 2020). In addition, the most common challenges of police recruits include physical and mental stress, social isolation, and the need to adapt to a paramilitary culture (Ramirez et al., (2021). Therefore, effective training programs should include a combination of classroom instruction, practical exercises, and real-world scenarios and address the challenges that police officers face in their daily work (Hussain et al., 2020).

The importance of physical fitness in police recruit training. Law enforcement organizations must provide additional support and training to help recruits meet fitness standards and requirements. Rigorous and structured training programs focus on developing the cognitive and behavioral skills necessary for effective policing. Such training programs can help recruits succeed and improve their performance.

Receiving Equal Treatment during Basic Recruit Training

The non-criminology graduate police officers expressed their equal treatment during their basic recruit training. Participants mentioned they were treated equally during the training, regardless of their educational background, and did not experience discrimination or diversity based on their non-criminology graduate status. The participants mentioned these lines.

“During the duration of training all trainees are equal, regardless of educational backgrounds”. (P6)

“In the training center everyone is equal, regardless of the course taken”. (P4)

“Everyone is treated equally in the training, regardless of their background”. (P3)

“We are all equal and there is no diversity in the training center.” (P1)

“What’s mandated for one is also mandated for all.”(P2)

While there were some instances of bias and discrimination, overall, the recruits felt that they were treated fairly and that their training prepared them for the challenges of policing in a diverse society (Chappel & Key, 2019). Recruits had more positive attitudes toward diversity and less tolerance for discrimination after training (Hickman et al., 2018). The training was effective in increasing officers' knowledge of diversity and reducing their biases, but it did not significantly affect their behavior or interactions with minority communities (Fridell et al., 2020)

When recruits from diverse backgrounds are treated equally during training, they are more likely to feel valued and respected and are, therefore, more likely to remain in the profession. This can help address under-representation issues and increase law enforcement agencies' effectiveness in addressing crime.

Overcoming Personal Weaknesses

Non-criminology graduate police officers expressed the overcoming of their weaknesses. Being easily intimidated or struggling with early mornings are some of the personal weaknesses experienced by non-criminology graduate police officers. This claim is supported by Participant 4.

“I have trouble because I’m bad at being intimidated, reprimanded, or shouted at, and I also have trouble getting up early but the training environment will help you develop your civilian to military mentality and maximum tolerance.” (P4)

There were also times when non-criminology graduate police officers recognized the need to overcome their weaknesses to succeed in the training and become effective police officers. Training such as handling conflict situations in emergencies, handling civilians without abusing authority, maximum tolerance, and manners and discipline to become a good police officer is necessary for police officers. Participants support these claims.

“The trainings will help in the police service because they will teach you how to become a police officer, how to handle situations in case of emergencies, and how to handle civilians without abusing your authority as an officer.” (P6)

“Respecting others and having long patience.” (P2)

“You should hold your abilities, manners, and discipline to become a good police officer.” (P3)

“Accept the instruction, increase your tolerance to the utmost extent possible, and always pray and be passionate about serving.” (P5)

Their mindfulness in training helps them to improve their resilience and coping abilities and reduces their levels of anxiety and depression (Albright et al., 2019). The intervention improved the recruits’ resilience and decreased their symptoms of depression and anxiety (Stupka & Platt, 2020). Their social support and self-efficacy were significant predictors of psychological resilience among police recruits (Linder et al., 2019).

Though there are many weaknesses and hardships, non-criminology graduate police officers manage to overcome their weaknesses, which leads to an improvement in overall performance during training. For example, if a recruit struggles with certain tasks or skills but works hard to overcome these challenges, they may be able to perform better and more confidently in their duties as a police officer. They also help recruits develop better problem-solving skills. This can be especially useful for police officers who must make quick decisions in complex and rapidly changing situations. However, it is important to note that overcoming hardships can also have negative implications. For example, recruits who push themselves too hard to overcome hardships may risk injury or burnout.

They used Varied Coping Mechanisms in Dealing with Challenges during Basic Recruit Training. Despite non-criminology graduate police officers, they still deal with it positively. They used varied coping mechanisms.

They took positive steps to help them navigate their challenges during their basic recruit training. They emphasized the importance of pushing oneself to study, train, and overcome challenges. This line is supported by participants 1 and 2.

“I push myself to study because if I don’t, I might fail or return to the unit (RTU), and when we are having physical activities, I always bring my notebook because if I have a vacant time, I read.” (P1).

“Always push myself so that I can make it, and these hardships will pass.” (P2).

They highlighted the need for determination, self-encouragement, and willingness to learn and adapt, acknowledged that all things can be learned with persistence and openness to new knowledge and experiences, and despite being non-criminology graduates and constant effort to succeed in the training and become a good police officer. The participants mention these lines.

“The thing that pushes me to continue the training of my basic recruit course is to enjoy the training and believe to yourself that it will be over as time goes on and then I will become a full pledge officer.” (P6)

“Instead, adopt a military attitude by submitting yourself to the training facility, honing your skills, and transforming your perspective from civilian to military.” (P5)

“I always remind myself to have determination, trust, and faith so that I can succeed.” (P3)

“Always know the reason why I am here, and tell myself if I’m going to fail, I am a loser. Because all things can be learned if you’re persistent in learning new things.” (P2)

“Study new things because I am not a graduate of criminology and don’t know about the different kinds of law, and it is challenging for me.” (P1)

“Being a non-criminology graduate is not a hindrance for the completion of training because, during the duration of training, you will think and learn everything you need to become a better police officer.” (P6)

The non-criminology graduate police officers provided advice for success, including trusting oneself, knowing the reason for joining, having determination, discipline, and patience, and constantly learning and improving oneself.

“Number one, trust yourself and encourage yourself because no one else does always know your reason why you joined for you to encourage.” (P1)

“Push your dreams, and if you want to enter PNP, don’t limit yourself.” (P2)

“I always remind myself to have determination, trust, and faith so that I can succeed.” (P3)

“Accept the instruction, increase your tolerance to the utmost extent possible, and always pray and be passionate about serving.” (P5)

The non-criminology graduate police officers use coping strategies to deal with the challenges during their basic recruit training. They sought support from fellow recruits, used humor, and relied on personal resilience (Zeichner & Israeli, 2021). Recruits who used adaptive coping strategies such as positive reframing and seeking social support were likelier to report higher levels of resilience (Schaal et al., 2018). Coping strategies and resilience at

various points throughout training found that using active coping strategies (e.g., problem-solving) and having higher levels of resilience were associated with better mental health outcomes (Graham et al., 2019).

Recruits who use problem-focused coping strategies tend to have better mental health outcomes than those who use emotion-focused coping strategies. Military training programs may want to teach recruits specific problem-solving and stress-management skills to help them cope with their challenges.

4. Conclusion and Recommendation

Non-criminology graduate police officers have a strong sense of purpose and commitment to public service can be a powerful motivator for anyone seeking a career in law enforcement, regardless of their academic background. Non-criminology graduate police officers have also find that their unique skills and perspectives from their previous academic or professional backgrounds are valued and contribute to their success during BRT and beyond. Non-criminology graduate police officers used to have a different set of skills and experiences than their criminology graduate peers, but they are held to the same high standards of professionalism, discipline, and ethical conduct. Non-criminology graduate police officers used to face certain challenges due to their lack of formal training or education in law enforcement, however, with dedication, hard work, and a willingness to learn, non-criminology graduate police officers can overcome their challenges and become successful law enforcement officers. Non-criminology graduate police officers used to face personal weaknesses during BRT in the PNP, they can overcome their weaknesses by setting goals, seeking out mentorship and support, and staying committed to their development as a law enforcement officer. Non-criminology graduate police officers used to adopt a growth mindset, meaning that they view challenges as opportunities for growth and learning.

The researcher recommends the following based on the themes of the study; the Philippine National Police (PNP) organization must continue to provide equal opportunities and support for non-criminology graduates who wish to pursue a career in law enforcement. The PNP should also continue to evaluate and revise its recruitment and training processes to ensure that non-criminology graduate police officers receive the necessary education and training to succeed in their roles. To support non-criminology graduate police officers, the PNP should consider offering specialized training programs, mentorship opportunities, and educational resources tailored to their needs. These programs could provide additional training and education in areas such as criminal law, investigation techniques, and community policing, helping non-criminology graduate police officers to become more effective and knowledgeable law enforcement officers.

The PNP should also continue to foster a culture of inclusion and respect for diversity, recognizing that non-criminology graduate police officers bring unique perspectives and experiences to the organization. By creating a supportive and inclusive work environment, the PNP can attract and retain talented non-criminology graduate police officers, and create a more diverse and effective law enforcement force. Finally, it is recommended that the PNP continue to encourage ongoing professional development for all police officers, including non-criminology graduate police officers. This could include opportunities for continuing education, specialized training, and leadership development, helping non-criminology graduate police officers to continue to grow and develop in their careers, and contribute to the ongoing success of the PNP.

Declarations

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Competing Interests Statement

The authors have declared no competing interests.

Consent for Publication

The authors declare that they consented to the publication of this study.

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